

Research Article

Energy-Aware Regression in Spiking Neural Networks for Autonomous Driving: A Comparative Study With Convolutional Networks

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As autonomous driving (AD) systems grow more complex, their rising computational demands pose significant energy and sustainability challenges. This paper investigates spiking neural networks (SNNs) as low-power alternatives to convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for regression tasks in AD. We introduce a membrane-potential (V_{mem}) decoding framework that converts binary spike trains into continuous outputs and propose the energy-to-error ratio (EER), a unified metric combining prediction error with energy consumption. Three CNN architectures (PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet) and their corresponding SNN variants are trained and evaluated using delta, latency, and rate encoding across varied parameter settings, with energy use and emissions logged. Delta-encoded SNNs achieve the highest EER, substantial energy savings with minimal performance loss, whereas CNNs, despite slightly better MSE, incur 10–20× higher energy costs. Rate encoding underperforms, and latency encoding, though improving relative error, demands excessive energy. Parameter tuning (threshold θ , temporal dynamics (S), membrane time constant (τ), and gain G) directly influences eco-efficiency. All experiments run on standard GPUs, showing SNNs can surpass CNNs in eco-efficiency without specialized hardware. Paired statistical tests confirm that only delta-encoded SNNs achieve significant EER improvements. This work presents a practical, energy-aware evaluation framework for neural architectures, establishing EER as a critical metric for sustainable machine learning in intelligent transport and beyond.

Keywords: autonomous driving; CO₂ emissions; eco-efficiency assessment; energy-to-error ratio (EER); neural network encoding; spiking neural networks (SNNs); sustainable artificial intelligence

1. Introduction

Spiking neural networks (SNNs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are key AI frameworks with distinct features. SNNs mimic the brain's spike-based communication system, aiming to replicate temporal neuronal dynamics for efficient, real-time processing and energy-saving applications, particularly in neuromorphic engineering

[1, 2]. CNNs, meanwhile, excel at processing grid-like data, such as images by extracting hierarchical spatial features, making them effective in visual tasks [3, 4].

Eco-efficiency is vital in autonomous driving (AD), balancing environmental sustainability with economic benefits. Autonomous vehicles (AVs) can reduce emissions, fuel use, and congestion [5, 6], while fostering innovation and sustainable tech development [7, 8]. Optimizing in-

vehicle machine learning (ML) models enhances energy efficiency (EE) and reduces the automotive sector’s carbon footprint.

Eco-efficient artificial intelligence (AI) focuses on sustainability in energy-intensive tasks, using advanced algorithms to cut power use without sacrificing performance [9–13].

A key research gap exists in comparing the eco-efficiency of CNNs and SNNs within AD contexts. CNNs are computationally heavy [14–17], while SNNs offer a lower energy usage through event-driven processing [18]. However, direct comparative studies remain scarce.

To evaluate these models holistically, metrics beyond accuracy, such as energy use and ecological impact, are essential [19–21]. A balanced eco-efficiency metric that integrates performance and energy consumption would clarify the model trade-offs [22–24], aiding in the selection of high-performing and sustainable ML systems.

Although simpler than full-scale AD pipelines, the Udacity self-driving simulator task captures key aspects of real-world regression challenges: varying lighting, road curvature, and steering dynamics, making it a widely adopted proxy for evaluating energy-aware perception-to-action models.

In the next section, dedicated to related work, we explore the existing literature and previous studies that provide essential context for our current research.

2. Related Work

The rise of AI in AD has improved performance but raised concerns about energy use and environmental impact. This section reviews efforts to enhance EE in AD, comparing CNNs and SNNs for their trade-offs between performance and eco-efficiency. It also examines sustainability metrics, advocating for approaches beyond traditional error-based evaluations. Finally, it explores Green AI in practice, emphasizing the balance between performance and EE in real-world ML applications.

2.1. EE in AD Systems. Energy-efficient AD systems are vital to reduce the environmental impact and boost economic sustainability. The high energy demands of AI-driven AD systems raise concerns about their carbon footprint. Efforts to address this focus on enhancing the EE of AI models, hardware, and software, enabling sustainable transportation advancements. The key challenges and strategies for minimizing energy use in AD are described below.

- Overview of the challenges posed by the growing computational requirements of AD systems.

The growing complexity of AD and the need for real-time decisions have sharply increased computational demands. AVs must analyze massive quantities of sensor inputs for activities such as recognizing objects, determining their positions, and strategizing paths, which all depend on powerful, energy-consuming processing. These demands are intensified by deep learning (DL) algorithms, which are essential but

resource-heavy for perception, control, and decision-making. Liu et al. [25] explored computing frameworks for AD, addressing performance metrics, technologies, and key challenges, particularly the difficulty of real-time decision-making in dynamic traffic, which can lead to accidents. Table 1 outlines the computational challenges across AD components based on their review.

- Existing approaches to address energy consumption and sustainability in AD applications.

The increasing computational load of AD systems raises EE concerns, prompting research into sustainable methods. Traditional strategies include hardware and software optimization using accelerators such as GPUs and TPUs for efficient NN execution. Recently, neuromorphic computing (N-HW), which mimics biological neural activity, has gained interest for its potential to significantly reduce energy use [26, 27]. Ary et al. summarize in [28] the current state of N-HW development. In terms of power consumption, most neuromorphic platforms are engineered for extreme EE, typically drawing between 1 and 5 W of power. For instance, the DYNAPs architecture [29] achieves real-time SNN emulation while consuming only 2 mW—orders of magnitude lower than conventional processors. At the higher end, SpiNNaker 2 [30] sustains a power envelope of approximately 5 W yet still supports large-scale DNNs, symbolic reasoning workloads, and high-performance computing applications. This balance of modest power draw and substantial computational throughput underscores the promise of N-HW for energy-constrained deployments.

Algorithmic methods such as pruning and quantization reduce model size and complexity, lowering energy use during training and inference. Transfer and federated learning further cut energy by minimizing data transmission and retraining needs. Energy-efficient NN architectures, especially SNNs, are gaining attention for their event-driven, low-power processing compared to standard DL models.

Research has proposed various strategies to boost EE in AD systems, including simulation-based testing to avoid costly physical trials. Metrics such as carbon footprint and energy-performance trade-offs are increasingly used to guide sustainable deployment. These efforts reflect the industry’s move toward eco-conscious AD development.

Table 2 summarizes energy-efficient training approaches, showing performance, energy, and complexity trade-offs.

2.2. Comparative Analysis of Neural Network Architectures. AI frameworks heavily depend on NNs for tasks from perception to decision-making. In contrast, AD demands real-time processing, exactness, and EE, necessitating a detailed comparison of NN models, such as CNNs, SNNs, and recurrent neural networks (RNNs). Table 3 summarizes their performance and EE in AD contexts.

TABLE 1: Overview of challenges posed by the growing computational requirements of AD systems.

Aspect	Description	Computational requirements	Challenges
Perception (e.g., object detection)	Processing raw sensor data from cameras, LiDAR, and radar to detect objects and surroundings	High	High computational load due to large data volumes and real-time processing requirements
Localization and mapping	Determining precise vehicle position and creating maps of the surrounding environment	High	Requires complex algorithms to integrate multiple data sources and achieve accuracy in real time
Path planning	Calculating optimal routes considering obstacles, traffic rules, and safety constraints	Medium	Demands dynamic updates and efficient algorithms to ensure real-time responsiveness
Control systems	Executing decisions on steering, braking, and acceleration to follow the planned path	Low	Minimal computational cost but sensitive to latency and accuracy for smooth vehicle operation
Decision-making	Real-time decision-making in complex scenarios, such as intersections or pedestrian crossings	High	Computationally intensive as it involves processing multiple inputs and applying advanced models
Sensor fusion	Combining data from multiple sensors (e.g., LiDAR, cameras, radar) to create a coherent picture	High	Synchronization and processing of diverse data streams require significant computational power
Redundancy and fault tolerance	Ensuring reliable system operation even in the case of sensor or subsystem failure	Medium	Requires parallel processing and backup algorithms to maintain system safety
Energy efficiency	Balancing performance with limited energy availability, especially in electric vehicles (EVs)	Medium	Computationally efficient algorithms are needed to optimize energy usage while maintaining safety

Note: Source: authors.

TABLE 2: Comparison of existing approaches to address energy consumption and sustainability in training models for AD applications.

Cite	Approach	Key features	Energy	Complexity
[31]	Model compression	Techniques such as pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation to reduce model size	Low	Medium
[32]	Efficient architectures	Use of lightweight models such as MobileNet, SqueezeNet, or custom-tailored neural architectures	Low	Low
[33]	SNNs	Event-driven processing mimics biological neurons, significantly reducing energy consumption	Low	High
[34]	Federated learning	Decentralized training on edge devices to reduce communication and energy overheads	Medium	High
[35]	Transfer learning	Leveraging pretrained models to reduce training time and energy	Low	Low
[36]	Green AI frameworks	Using tools such as CodeCarbon or CarbonTracker to monitor and optimize energy usage during training	Medium	Medium
[37]	Algorithmic optimization	Use of more efficient training algorithms, such as adaptive gradient descent or reduced backpropagation steps	Low	Medium

Note: Source: authors.

TABLE 3: Comparative overview of NN architectures.

Cite	Architecture	Performance	Energy
[15]	CNN	High accuracy in perception tasks such as object detection and lane tracking	Medium
[38]	RNN	Effective in sequence prediction but limited for real-time image processing	Medium
[55]	SNN	Competitive for certain tasks but often requires more advanced tuning	High
[39]	Transformer models	State-of-the-art performance for vision tasks (e.g., vision transformers)	Low to medium
[40]	Lightweight architectures	Moderate accuracy compared to full-scale CNNs	High
[41]	Hybrid (CNN + SNN)	Balances CNN's accuracy with SNN's energy efficiency	High

Note: Source: authors.

NN architectures vary in suitability for AD. CNNs are strong in image tasks such as detection and localization, but demand optimization for real-time EE. SNNs offer better energy use but face training challenges. RNNs handle sequences well (e.g., trajectory prediction) yet are computationally heavy. Transformers provide a strong understanding of the global context, but their high energy and latency make them less practical for edge deployment [31]. Hybrid or lightweight models, combining CNNs and SNNs, are promising for real-world energy-conscious AD.

Focusing on CNNs versus SNNs, several studies highlight performance and energy trade-offs. Chakraborty et al. [32] reported a 70% energy reduction with hybrid SNNs. Ankit et al. [33] showed up to 85% savings using memristive hardware. Deng et al. [20] found that SNNs used 10x less energy but had 5%–10% lower accuracy. Spike-YOLO [34] reduced the energy by 50% with 3% accuracy loss. ANN-to-SNN conversions matched CNN accuracy on CIFAR-10 [35] and MNIST [36], using 4–10x less energy [37]. SNNs also outperformed CNNs in acoustic monitoring [38], integer-valued inference [39], and ECG classification [40] with significant energy savings.

However, most studies focus on classification or specific contexts, with little attention to regression tasks such as steering or distance prediction in AD. There is also a lack of unified metrics to assess both performance and eco-efficiency. This study addresses these gaps by comparing CNNs and SNNs on regression tasks in AD, introducing a novel framework to evaluate sustainable neural network design.

2.3. Metrics for Sustainability in AI. As AI progresses, the significance of sustainability has escalated, instigating a transformation in the methodologies employed for model evaluation. Traditionally, metrics have been used to measure the performance of models, each with a different purpose and focus as we summarize below:

- Mean Squared Error (MSE) [41]: This measures the average squared difference between predicted and actual values. Lower MSE indicates better performance.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2. \quad (1)$$

- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) [41]: A variant of MSE, providing error in the same units as the output emphasizing larger errors.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}. \quad (2)$$

- R-squared (R^2) [41]: It indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the model with ($R^2 = 1$) indicating perfect predictions.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}. \quad (3)$$

- Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) [42]: This evaluates prediction accuracy by expressing errors as a percentage of actual values. It is useful for understanding relative error but sensitive to small values in the denominator.

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100. \quad (4)$$

- Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE) [43]: It adjusts MSE for scale differences, making it more interpretable. It is useful for comparing models across datasets.

$$\text{NMSE} = \frac{\text{MSE}}{\text{Variance of } y}. \quad (5)$$

However, as the computational requirements of these systems escalate, there has been an increasing acknowledgment of the necessity to assess the ecological consequences of both model training and implementation. This has led to the adoption of eco-efficiency metrics, which measure energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and computational efficiency during model training and inference. A selection of the most widely utilized metrics is presented below.

- Carbon Intensity (CI) [44]: This measures the CO₂-emitted per kilowatt-hour (kWh) of energy used and provides a direct measure of environmental impact.

$$CI = \frac{\text{Total CO}_2 \text{ Emissions (grams)}}{\text{Total Energy Consumed (kWh)}} \quad (6)$$

- EE [45]: It quantifies the ratio of the useful computational workload performed by an AI/ML system to the total energy (ETotal) consumed. It is used to compare energy utilization across AI systems.

$$EE = \frac{\text{Useful Workload (e.g., FLOPs)}}{\text{Total Energy Consumed (kWh)}} \quad (7)$$

- Energy Delay Product (EDP) [46]: It evaluates the trade-off between energy consumption and processing delay (time). It emphasizes both energy savings and speed.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EDP} &= \text{Energy Consumption (kWh)} \\ &\times \text{Training Time (Hours)}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [47]: It considers the full lifecycle environmental impact of ML systems from development to disposal. It is used in sustainable AI projects to optimize long-term impacts.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LCA} &= \sum_i (\text{Resource Consumption}_i + \text{Emissions}_i) \\ &\times \text{Impact Factor}_i. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

- Accuracy-to-Energy Ratio (AER) [48]: It balances accuracy and EE in a single metric and balances performance and eco-efficiency. Higher values indicate better eco-performance.

$$\text{AER} = \frac{\text{Accuracy}}{\text{Energy Consumption (kWh)}} \quad (10)$$

In AD, where edge device energy use impacts feasibility, eco-efficiency metrics are essential. Equation (6) sets the environmental baseline, while 7 measures AI performance per unit of energy. Metrics, such as 8, highlight trade-offs between processing power and energy use, and 9 provides a full life-cycle view of sustainability, from resource extraction to disposal. Composite indicators, such as 10, balance performance with eco-efficiency, supporting sustainable AI development.

Furthermore, the environmental metrics of Castellanos-Nieves et al. [49] assess runtime, CPU/GPU/TPU energy use, and RAM consumption, critical in data-heavy tasks. Broader metrics such as ETotal and carbon equivalent ($\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}}$) give a holistic view, linking computational efficiency with ecological impact.

2.4. Energy-to-Error Ratio (EER). Although current metrics offer insights into environmental impact, they often fail to balance eco-efficiency with model performance, particularly when comparing CNNs and SNNs in tasks such as AD. CNNs usually deliver lower prediction error but consume

more energy, whereas SNNs are more energy-efficient at the cost of some accuracy.

Despite its straightforward formulation, AER is based solely on categorical accuracy and becomes insensitive to energy savings as accuracy approaches 100%, limiting its ability to balance eco-efficiency with model performance when comparing CNNs and SNNs in tasks such as AD. For any given task, both CNNs and SNNs provide an accuracy and an energy consumption metric, and AER computes a simple ratio of these. However, this approach obscures critical nuances:

- Classification-only scope: AER is inherently defined for categorical output, i.e., accuracy (or its complement, error rate). In AD tasks involving continuous outputs, such as steering angle prediction or distance estimation, performance is measured by continuous metrics (e.g., MSE, MAPE), for which accuracy is undefined. Thus, AER cannot be applied to regression scenarios without artificially binarizing or discretizing outputs, which distorts both error and energy interpretations.
- Sensitivity collapse at high accuracy: As accuracy improves and approaches 100%, small absolute changes in accuracy translate into negligible changes in AER, even if they correspond to large energy differences. For example, improving the accuracy from 98% to 99% at the cost of doubling energy consumption might produce almost the same AER, failing to penalize energy-inefficient gains. This saturation effect means that AER cannot discern trade-offs in the regime where models are near state-of-the-art performance.
- Lack of unified interpretation across tasks: Because the AER denominator and units depend on task-specific definitions of accuracy, comparing eco-efficiency across classification and regression tasks becomes inconsistent. The metric loses meaning when accuracy scales differ (e.g., percentage points versus millimeter errors), making cross-task or cross-domain comparisons unreliable.

Together, these limitations mean that while AER can offer a rough eco-comparison for classification benchmarks, it fails to provide a balanced, interpretable, and generalizable metric when comparing CNNs and SNNs across the diverse tasks required in AD.

In contrast, we propose the EER, as the ETotal consumed was divided by the task error, regardless of task type.

$$\text{EER} = \frac{1}{\text{MSE} \cdot \text{Energy Consumption (kWh)}} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) allows the Error term to be defined in a flexible way, depending on the particular task. In the context of classification, the error may be represented not only as $1 - \text{Accuracy}$ but also in relation to precision, recall, or $F1$ -derived error metrics. EER is suitable for scenarios prioritizing balanced class performance over overall accuracy. As detailed in Section 2.3, regression alternatives encompass MSE, RMSE, MAPE, or NMSE, for cross-dataset

comparisons. In the present work, we adopt MSE because it is continuous, differentiable, and widely established in regression tasks. In addition, the quadratic penalty results in large deviations in steering-angle predictions, which are vital for AD. The choice of MSE thus provides both practical relevance and consistency with the existing literature, while maintaining the generality of the EER framework for other metrics.

The EER offers several advantages:

- **Task-agnostic measurement:** This works uniformly with continuous (e.g., MSE) or categorical (e.g., 1-Accuracy) error metrics.
- **Direct eco-efficiency reflection:** This quantifies the exact energy required per unit of error, highlighting models that achieve low error with minimal energy.
- **Sensitivity across regimes:** This maintains meaningful comparisons even at high performance levels, avoiding the saturation issues of AER.
- **Comparative clarity:** This enables consistent cross-model and cross-task eco-efficiency analysis without arbitrary scaling or discretization.
- **Interpretation:** EER measures energy per unit error, higher EER values indicate higher eco-efficiency, as the model spends less energy to achieve each unit of error.
- **Trends:** A constant EER implies proportional changes in energy and error, whereas a lower EER for one model shows that it can achieve the same or lower error with less energy. This direct ratio therefore clearly reflects eco-efficiency trade-offs.

Generalizability: Because Error can represent any continuous or categorical performance metric, EER applies uniformly across regression and classification tasks, unlike AER.

To clarify how EER solves the limitations of AER, as mentioned before, three issues arise with AER: First, it is restricted to classification accuracy and therefore cannot be generalized to regression; second, it suffers from sensitivity collapse as Accuracy \rightarrow 1, leading to instability, and third, it lacks a unified interpretation across tasks. EER overcomes the three limitations through task-agnosticity, numerical stability, and consistent interpretability. To make this contrast concrete, Table 4 presents a toy example. Both models consume the same energy (10 Wh), but AER values appear very close (490 vs. 475), suggesting similar eco-efficiency. In contrast, EER highlights a clear separation (500 vs. 200), directly reflecting that the CNN achieves lower error for the same energy budget.

EER quantifies how effectively a model reduces error per unit of energy, offering a holistic eco-efficiency measure. Unlike AER, which evaluates trade-offs within a single architecture such as quantized CNNs, EER enables cross-architecture comparisons by capturing core performance-to-energy dynamics. This makes EER ideal for assessing CNNs and SNNs, which differ in computational principles and energy profiles. Table 5 outlines the unique contributions of each metric.

TABLE 4: AER and EER compared at fixed energy.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Error	Energy (Wh)	AER	EER
CNN	98	0.02	10	490	500
SNN	95	0.05	10	475	200

Note: Source: authors.

Introducing EER enables eco-efficiency comparisons across different architectures, advancing energy-conscious AI by prioritizing minimal computational resource use.

3. Methodology

This section presents the dataset and methodology for comparing SNNs and CNNs in AD tasks, focusing on preparation, encoding, compression, and evaluation. Using `snnTorch` library encoding methods (rate, latency, delta), traditional datasets are adapted for SNNs, with parameter variations analyzed for their effects on performance and eco-efficiency. Afterward, we compress the data into `h5py` format to ensure storage efficiency and data fidelity. Ecological impacts, including CO₂ emissions and energy use, are tracked using the `CodeCarbon` library [50].

PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet, each implemented as both a traditional CNN and as an SNN, are trained on the original Udacity dataset (for CNNs) and the corresponding spike-encoded versions (for SNNs). Regression experiments measure the predictive performance and energy consumption of each model under Delta, Latency, and Rate encoding schemes. We evaluated performance using MSE and MAPE, and computed EER to capture the energy-to-error trade-off, enabling a direct comparison of eco-efficiency across all six architectures and encoding configurations. By spanning three distinct network designs, our study ensures that the observed trends in accuracy, energy use, and eco-efficiency generalize beyond any single model.

To ensure fairness, all CNN and SNN experiments were conducted in identical settings: the same datasets, pre-processing, 80/20 train/validation split, optimizer (Adam with learning rate 10^{-3}), batch size, and 40 training epochs. Each configuration was tested multiple times with varying random seeds to mitigate initialization sensitivity. Fairness was further assessed through paired-run statistical tests that compared each SNN encoding (Delta, Rate, and Latency) against the CNN baseline, with results summarized in Table 6 in terms of mean differences, confidence intervals, effect sizes, and Bonferroni-adjusted significance levels.

We deliberately select PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet to span a representative range of capacity and computational cost in end-to-end steering on the Udacity simulator. PilotNet serves as a canonical medium-scale baseline that is extensively documented in prior work on end-to-end driving and remains a standard point of reference in this domain. LaksNet provides a literature-backed, compact alternative with substantially fewer parameters than PilotNet, enabling a mid-size comparison under the same task and dataset. Finally, MiniNet is an ultra-compact architecture to probe the low-parameter, edge-oriented regime, where energy constraints are most

TABLE 5: Comparison of integrated metrics EER and AER.

Metric	Definition	Use case	Gap addressed
AER	Measures the ratio of accuracy lost to energy saved during architectural optimizations	Comparing modifications within the same model (e.g., quantized or discretized CNNs)	Balances energy savings and accuracy drop in trade-off scenarios
EER	Quantifies how much “error reduction” (inverse of error) is achieved per unit of energy consumed.	Comparing different architectures (e.g., CNNs vs. SNNs) or the eco-efficiency of different models	Highlights overall eco-efficiency by linking energy consumption to performance improvement directly

Note: Source: authors.

pronounced. The integration of these three frameworks validates our findings about precision, power usage, and EER, highlighting that we do not depend on any specific architecture, thus maintaining uniformity across various network depths and parameter scales.

3.1. Network Architectures. We evaluated three convolutional networks, PilotNet [51], LaksNet [52], and a minimal three-layer MiniNet. CNN versions process raw image frames and provide well-established baselines for regression accuracy and energy consumption in the Udacity Self-Driving Car Simulator [53]. Their SNN adaptations replace standard activations with event-driven, leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neurons, operating on spike-encoded inputs to achieve real-time, energy-efficient regression. By comparing these six architectures, we systematically investigate how network depth, parameter count, and spiking dynamics influence the trade-off between predictive performance and eco-efficiency.

3.1.1. PilotNet. Developed by NVIDIA in 2016 from the DAVE-2 project (Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency AV [54]), the CNN architecture described in [51] consists of 9 layers: a normalization layer, 5 convolutional layers, and 3 fully connected layers. The input image is split into YUV planes (brightness and color) before being processed by the network (see Table 7).

Five convolutional layers were optimized through experimental trials for feature extraction. The first three used 5×5 kernels with 2×2 stride, while the last two used 3×3 nonstrided kernels. These were followed by three fully connected layers that output the steering angle. Although these layers act as a steering controller, end-to-end training blurs the distinction between feature extraction and control.

The PilotNet architecture was converted into an SNN by inserting spiking leaky layers after each convolutional and dense layer (except the flattening layer), enabling event-driven, energy-efficient processing suitable for regression tasks. As shown in Table 8, the convolutional layers remain unchanged from the original CNN, extracting features, while the fully connected layers generate control outputs.

3.1.2. LaksNet. Developed by Polamreddy and Zhang in [52] for end-to-end steering in the Udacity simulator, the LaksNet consists of 4 convolutional layers followed by 3 fully connected layers. It processes raw 66×200 RGB frames through progressively downsampled feature maps before flattening to a 3840-dimensional vector for regression. Its

compact design results in a total of 557,781 parameters (Table 9).

This CNN is converted into an SNN by inserting a spiking Leaky layer (zero parameters) immediately after each convolutional and linear layer, thus enabling event-driven propagation for energy-efficient regression (Table 10).

3.1.3. MiniNet. As an additional, ultracompact baseline, we designed MiniNet, a three-convolutional-layer CNN, followed by global pooling and a small head. This self-made architecture has only 34,657 parameters (Table 11).

This CNN is converted into an SNN by inserting Leaky spiking layers after each convolutional and linear layer, enabling sparse, event-driven feature extraction and regression (Table 12).

In SNNs, the LIF neuron model forms the fundamental basis of the leaky layer, which manages temporal data. It maintains a dynamic membrane potential (V_{mem}), which integrates inputs over time and decays toward a resting state based on the leak parameter (β). Mathematically, V_{mem} at time t is updated as follows:

$$V_{\text{mem}}(t) = \beta \cdot V_{\text{mem}}(t-1) + \text{Input}(t). \quad (12)$$

Higher β (e.g., 0.9) retains past input longer. When V_{mem} reaches a threshold (e.g., 0.5), the neuron fires, resets (or not, depending on use), and propagates a spike, enabling event-driven, energy-efficient computation. This leaky mechanism acts as short-term memory, aiding temporal sequence processing, such as in time-series tasks.

In our SNN adaptation of PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet, the final leaky layer does not reset after firing, allowing continuous V_{mem} buildup for regression outputs such as steering angle. This dynamic and biologically inspired behavior integrates temporal and spatial features effectively, supporting energy-efficient learning.

3.2. Data Preparation. This subsection outlines the dataset creation and preprocessing steps for training and evaluating all six architectures, PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet as traditional CNNs, along with their corresponding SNN adaptations. Raw images from a driving simulator were preprocessed, augmented, and encoded into spike-based representations using the `snnTorch` library. Various encoding methods, rate, latency, and delta were applied to create datasets with different parameter settings. To reduce computational load and improve reusability, transformed datasets were compressed and stored as `h5py` files. The

TABLE 6: Full statistical test results across models and encodings.

	Model	Encoding	Metric	CNN $\mu \pm \sigma$	SNN $\mu \pm \sigma$	Mean Δ	95% CI	Cohen's d	P_{adj}	Decision
0	LaksNet	Delta	MSE	0.0550 \pm 0.0006	0.2139 \pm 0.0015	0.158930	[0.1571, 0.1608]	90.23	1.08 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
1	LaksNet	Delta	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0001 \pm 0.0000	-0.000103	[-0.0001, -0.0001]	-61.38	7.41 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
2	LaksNet	Delta	EER	64700.7820 \pm 979.8057	134388.4689 \pm 1516.2915	69687.686927	[68370.7878, 71004.5861]	55.53	1.22 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
3	LaksNet	Delta	MAPE	12362.5854 \pm 134.6531	9034.9975 \pm 19.3996	-3327.587917	[-3462.5352, -3192.6407]	-25.88	5.55 \times 10 ⁻⁸	Reject H0
4	LaksNet	Rate	MSE	0.0550 \pm 0.0006	0.1217 \pm 0.0005	0.066721	[0.0658, 0.0676]	76.59	2.45 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
5	LaksNet	Rate	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0020 \pm 0.0000	0.001798	[0.0018, 0.0018]	170.03	4.54 \times 10 ⁻¹²	Reject H0
6	LaksNet	Rate	EER	64700.7820 \pm 979.8057	3020.9450 \pm 34.1547	-61679.837037	[-62720.0869, -60639.5871]	-62.22	6.92 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
7	LaksNet	Rate	MAPE	12362.5854 \pm 134.6531	40.1697 \pm 0.3109	-12322.415760	[-12463.4642, -12181.3673]	-91.68	9.97 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
8	LaksNet	Latency	MSE	0.0550 \pm 0.0006	0.1096 \pm 0.0006	0.054622	[0.0536, 0.0556]	55.92	1.18 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
9	LaksNet	Latency	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0021 \pm 0.0000	0.001903	[0.0019, 0.0019]	136.30	1.37 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
10	LaksNet	Latency	EER	64700.7820 \pm 979.8057	3571.7429 \pm 50.6933	-61129.039091	[-62181.4016, -60076.6766]	-60.96	7.67 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
11	LaksNet	Latency	MAPE	12362.5854 \pm 134.6531	6.1748 \pm 0.0216	-12356.410654	[-12497.7182, -12215.1031]	-91.77	9.92 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
12	MimiNet	Delta	MSE	0.0647 \pm 0.0003	0.2088 \pm 0.0009	0.144127	[0.1430, 0.1453]	131.83	1.62 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
13	MimiNet	Delta	EnergyCost	0.0001 \pm 0.0000	0.0000 \pm 0.0000	-0.000120	[-0.0001, -0.0001]	-56.05	1.17 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
14	MimiNet	Delta	EER	49030.0213 \pm 733.8863	204182.1023 \pm 2919.9020	155152.080923	[151715.3984, 158588.7635]	47.38	2.70 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
15	MimiNet	Delta	MAPE	12047.1839 \pm 120.0340	6232.2604 \pm 31.8094	-5814.923471	[-5967.4827, -5662.3643]	-40.00	6.30 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
16	MimiNet	Rate	MSE	0.0647 \pm 0.0003	0.1365 \pm 0.0009	0.071786	[0.0710, 0.0726]	94.19	8.71 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
17	MimiNet	Rate	EnergyCost	0.0001 \pm 0.0000	0.0008 \pm 0.0000	0.000614	[0.0006, 0.0006]	229.94	1.00 \times 10 ⁻¹²	Reject H0
18	MimiNet	Rate	EER	49030.0213 \pm 733.8863	9259.5901 \pm 126.0784	-39770.431188	[-40494.2250, -39046.6374]	-57.66	1.01 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0
19	MimiNet	Rate	MAPE	12047.1839 \pm 120.0340	112.6373 \pm 0.4500	-11934.546520	[-12060.5961, -11808.4969]	-99.36	6.67 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
20	MimiNet	Latency	MSE	0.0647 \pm 0.0003	0.1440 \pm 0.0007	0.079321	[0.0785, 0.0801]	103.85	1.08 \times 10 ⁻¹⁰	Reject H0
21	MimiNet	Latency	EnergyCost	0.0001 \pm 0.0000	0.0008 \pm 0.0000	0.000636	[0.0006, 0.0006]	142.32	5.35 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
22	MimiNet	Latency	EER	49030.0213 \pm 733.8863	8704.0856 \pm 77.3731	-40325.935693	[-41122.6129, -39529.2585]	-53.12	1.11 \times 10 ⁻¹¹	Reject H0
23	MimiNet	Latency	MAPE	12047.1839 \pm 120.0340	45.5513 \pm 0.1986	-12001.632578	[-12127.5945, -11875.6706]	-99.99	1.53 \times 10 ⁻⁹	Reject H0

TABLE 6: Continued.

	Model	Encoding	Metric	CNN $\mu \pm \sigma$	SNN $\mu \pm \sigma$	Mean Δ	95% CI	Cohen's d	P_{adj}	Decision
24	PilotNet	Delta	MSE	0.0588 \pm 0.0005	0.2146 \pm 0.0011	0.155794	[0.1545, 0.1571]	122.62	6.46 $\times 10^{-11}$	Reject H0
25	PilotNet	Delta	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0001 \pm 0.0000	-0.000126	[-0.0001, -0.0001]	-53.58	2.33 $\times 10^{-11}$	Reject H0
26	PilotNet	Delta	EER	47295.7860 \pm 806.5473	117365.7349 \pm 1870.5047	70069.948936	[67740.4549, 72399.4430]	31.57	1.46 $\times 10^{-9}$	Reject H0
27	PilotNet	Delta	MAPE	12817.7512 \pm 143.4549	7834.1114 \pm 58.1182	-4983.639752	[-5164.4684, -4802.8111]	-28.92	2.06 $\times 10^{-8}$	Reject H0
28	PilotNet	Rate	MSE	0.0588 \pm 0.0005	0.0374 \pm 0.0003	-0.021365	[-0.0218, -0.0209]	-48.00	3.18 $\times 10^{-8}$	Reject H0
29	PilotNet	Rate	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0021 \pm 0.0000	0.001957	[0.0019, 0.0020]	127.34	2.53 $\times 10^{-9}$	Reject H0
30	PilotNet	Rate	EER	47295.7860 \pm 806.5473	8606.7602 \pm 59.8924	-38689.025792	[-39576.9720, -37801.0796]	-45.73	1.93 $\times 10^{-11}$	Reject H0
31	PilotNet	Rate	MAPE	12817.7512 \pm 143.4549	63.4012 \pm 0.2465	-12754.349932	[-12905.0273, -12603.6726]	-88.83	3.23 $\times 10^{-9}$	Reject H0
32	PilotNet	Latency	MSE	0.0588 \pm 0.0005	0.1065 \pm 0.0004	0.047718	[0.0472, 0.0483]	92.83	1.17 $\times 10^{-10}$	Reject H0
33	PilotNet	Latency	EnergyCost	0.0002 \pm 0.0000	0.0023 \pm 0.0000	0.002127	[0.0021, 0.0021]	132.17	9.37 $\times 10^{-11}$	Reject H0
34	PilotNet	Latency	EER	47295.7860 \pm 806.5473	3799.8833 \pm 72.4371	-43495.902659	[-44324.7587, -42667.0466]	-55.07	1.60 $\times 10^{-11}$	Reject H0
35	PilotNet	Latency	MAPE	12817.7512 \pm 143.4549	21.1715 \pm 0.1789	-12796.579692	[-12947.1885, -12645.9708]	-89.17	1.27 $\times 10^{-9}$	Reject H0

Note: Source: authors.

TABLE 7: PilotNet CNN architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameter
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 24, 31, 98)	1824
relu (ReLU)	(None, 24, 31, 98)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(None, 36, 14, 47)	21,636
relu 1 (ReLU)	(None, 36, 14, 47)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(None, 48, 5, 22)	43,248
relu 2 (ReLU)	(None, 48, 5, 22)	0
conv2d 3 (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 3, 20)	27,712
relu 3 (ReLU)	(None, 64, 3, 20)	0
conv2d 4 (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 1, 18)	36,928
relu 4 (ReLU)	(None, 64, 1, 18)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64, 1, 18)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 1152)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 100)	115,300
relu 5 (ReLU)	(None, 100)	0
dense 1 (Dense)	(None, 50)	5050
relu 6 (ReLU)	(None, 50)	0
dense 2 (Dense)	(None, 10)	510
relu 7 (ReLU)	(None, 10)	0
dense 3 (Dense)	(None, 1)	11

Note: The network has about 27 million connections and 250,000 parameters. Source: authors. Model: “sequential”. Total params: 252,219. Trainable params: 252,219. Nontrainable params: 0.

TABLE 8: SNN adaptation of the PilotNet architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
conv2d (Conv2D)	(-1, 31, 98, 24)	1824
leaky 1 (Leaky)	(-1, 31, 98, 24)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(-1, 14, 47, 36)	21,636
leaky 2 (Leaky)	(-1, 14, 47, 36)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(-1, 5, 22, 48)	43,248
leaky 3 (Leaky)	(-1, 5, 22, 48)	0
conv2d 3 (Conv2D)	(-1, 3, 20, 64)	27,712
leaky 4 (Leaky)	(-1, 3, 20, 64)	0
conv2d 4 (Conv2D)	(-1, 1, 18, 64)	36,928
leaky 5 (Leaky)	(-1, 1, 18, 64)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(-1, 1152)	0
dense (Dense)	(-1, 100)	115,300
leaky 6 (Leaky)	(-1, 100)	0
dense 1 (Dense)	(-1, 50)	5050
leaky 7 (Leaky)	(-1, 50)	0
dense 2 (Dense)	(-1, 10)	510
leaky 8 (Leaky)	(-1, 10)	0
dense 3 (Dense)	(-1, 1)	11
Leaky 9 (Output)	([-1, 1], [-1, 1])	0

Note: Source: authors. Model: “sequential”. Total params: 252,219. Trainable params: 252,219. Nontrainable params: 0.

section also explains the rationale behind the encoding methods, the compression strategy, and the steps taken to ensure ecological efficiency. These preparations enable a fair and consistent comparison between CNN and SNN architectures.

3.2.1. Dataset. To validate our approach, we used a dataset from the Udacity open-source simulator [53], a widely adopted tool for training CNNs in AD. It provides two environments: one for training data collection and one for testing.

TABLE 9: LaksNet CNN architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 24, 31, 98)	1824
relu (ReLU)	(None, 24, 31, 98)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(None, 36, 14, 47)	21,636
relu 1 (ReLU)	(None, 36, 14, 47)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(None, 48, 5, 22)	43,248
relu 2 (ReLU)	(None, 48, 5, 22)	0
conv2d 3 (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 3, 20)	27,712
relu 3 (ReLU)	(None, 64, 3, 20)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 3840)	0
dense (Linear)	(None, 120)	460,920
relu 4 (ReLU)	(None, 120)	0
dense 1 (Linear)	(None, 20)	2420
relu 5 (ReLU)	(None, 20)	0
dense 2 (Linear)	(None, 1)	21

Note: The network has about 0.56 million connections and 0.558 million parameters. Source: authors. Model: “sequential”. Total params: 557,781. Trainable params: 557,781. Nontrainable params: 0.

TABLE 10: SNN adaptation of the LaksNet architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
conv2d (Conv2D)	(-1, 24, 31, 98)	1824
leaky 1 (Leaky)	(-1, 24, 31, 98)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(-1, 36, 14, 47)	21,636
leaky 2 (Leaky)	(-1, 36, 14, 47)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(-1, 48, 5, 22)	43,248
leaky 3 (Leaky)	(-1, 48, 5, 22)	0
conv2d 3 (Conv2D)	(-1, 64, 3, 20)	27,712
leaky 4 (Leaky)	(-1, 64, 3, 20)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(-1, 3840)	0
dense (Linear)	(-1, 120)	460,920
leaky 5 (Leaky)	(-1, 120)	0
dense 1 (Linear)	(-1, 20)	2420
leaky 6 (Leaky)	(-1, 20)	0
dense 2 (Linear)	(-1, 1)	21
leaky 7 (Output)	([-1, 1], [-1, 1])	0

Note: Source: authors. Model: “sequential”. Total params: 557,781. Trainable params: 557,781. Nontrainable params: 0.

The simulation setup includes three cameras (front and sides) and sensors capturing speed, throttle, brake, and steering angle. The dataset comprises 23,244 images (7748 per camera) at 160×320 resolution, totaling 362 MB. A CSV file (3.6 MB) records sensor data for each frame, containing 7748 entries.

The dataset, consisting of images and CSV logs, was encoded by applying the methods that we explain in the next subsection.

3.2.2. Encoding Methods. Spikes, sparsity, and static suppression are key features in SNNs that mimic biological systems, improve computational efficiency, and enhance noise robustness [55]. To convert data into spike-based formats, the `snnTorch` library provides rate, latency, and delta encoding methods, chosen for their PyTorch compatibility. These techniques enable efficient data pre-processing and integration within the existing ML workflows.

TABLE 11: MiniNet CNN architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 31, 98)	1216
relu (ReLU)	(None, 16, 31, 98)	0
max pool2d (MaxPool2D)	(None, 16, 15, 49)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 6, 23)	12,832
relu 1 (ReLU)	(None, 32, 6, 23)	0
max pool2d 1 (MaxPool2D)	(None, 32, 3, 11)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 1, 9)	18,496
relu 2 (ReLU)	(None, 64, 1, 9)	0
adaptive avg pool2d	(None, 64, 1, 1)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 64)	0
dense (Linear)	(None, 32)	2080
relu 3 (ReLU)	(None, 32)	0
dense 1 (Linear)	(None, 1)	33

Note: The network has about 35,000 connections and 34,657 parameters. Source: authors. Model: "sequential". Total params: 34,657. Trainable params: 34,657. Nontrainable params: 0.

TABLE 12: SNN adaptation of the MiniNet architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
conv2d (Conv2D)	(-1, 16, 31, 98)	1216
leaky 1 (Leaky)	(-1, 16, 31, 98)	0
max pool2d (MaxPool2D)	(-1, 16, 15, 49)	0
conv2d 1 (Conv2D)	(-1, 32, 6, 23)	12,832
leaky 2 (Leaky)	(-1, 32, 6, 23)	0
max pool2d 1 (MaxPool2D)	(-1, 32, 3, 11)	0
conv2d 2 (Conv2D)	(-1, 64, 1, 9)	18,496
leaky 3 (Leaky)	(-1, 64, 1, 9)	0
adaptive avg pool2d	(-1, 64, 1, 1)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(-1, 64)	0
dense (Linear)	(-1, 32)	2080
leaky 4 (Leaky)	(-1, 32)	0
dense 1 (Linear)	(-1, 1)	33
leaky 5 (Output)	([-1, 1], [-1, 1])	0

Note: Source: authors. Model: "sequential". Total params: 34,657. Trainable params: 34,657. Nontrainable params: 0.

3.2.2.1. Rate Encoding. Rate encoding in SNNs encodes information via neuron firing rates, where higher input magnitudes lead to more frequent spikes [56]. For instance, in grayscale images, white pixels (value 255) trigger spikes with 100% probability, while black pixels (value 0) do not.

This study uses rate encoding from the `snnTorch` library to convert nonspike data into spike trains, capturing temporal dynamics (S) over sequence length S , due to its robustness to noise. Inputs are transformed into sequences of binary values $X_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$ across a defined number of time steps (temporal dynamics). Each normalized input feature $X_{i,j}$ is treated as the probability of a Bernoulli trial $R_{i,j} \sim B(n, p)$, where the number of trials is n and the probability of success (spiking) is $p = X_{i,j}$, determining spike occurrences and forming a rate-coded sequence representing the original input. The probability of a spike occurring is explicitly calculated as follows:

$$P(R_{i,j} = 1) = X_{i,j} = 1 - P(R_{i,j} = 0). \quad (13)$$

In our dataset, the pixel value directly determines the peak probability.

We selected S values of 25 and 50 to study the effect of time resolution: 50 is exactly the double of 25, allowing us to observe how doubling the number of timesteps impacts spike-train fidelity and network performance, while keeping both values relatively low to avoid excessively large datasets. The G parameters (0.5 and 1.0) span the full activation spectrum, 0.5 represents a moderate scaling of pixel intensity, and 1.0 doubles that input drive, so together they let us explore both mid-range and maximum firing-rate regimes. For each (S, G) pair, we generated an independent dataset and split it 80% and 20% (train/val) with a fixed seed (42) to ensure exact reproducibility.

The output of this step, it will be compressed as explained in the following section.

3.2.2.2. Latency Encoding. Latency encoding represents information through spike timing, where higher input intensities result in earlier spikes, creating a sparse, efficient, and noise-robust temporal encoding method [55]. This biologically inspired approach mirrors how neurons use spike timing to convey stimulus intensity. The process is often modeled using an RC circuit, where I_{in} is the input current proportional to the pixel intensity, R and C are the resistance and capacitance of the circuit, determining the time constant $\tau = R \cdot C$, t is the time elapsed, and $V(t)$ is the V_{mem} at time t .

$$V(t) = I_{in}R \left[1 - e^{-t/RC} \right]. \quad (14)$$

A spike is emitted when $V(t)$ reaches a predefined threshold V_{thr} . Solving for the time t at which this occurs gives

$$t = RC \ln \left(\frac{I_{in}R}{I_{in}R - V_{thr}} \right). \quad (15)$$

For simplicity, if $R = 1$, the equation reduces to

$$t = \tau \ln \left(\frac{I_{in}}{I_{in} - V_{thr}} \right). \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) shows that higher inputs (I_{in}) charge $V(t)$ faster, causing earlier spikes, while lower inputs delay or suppress spikes if the V_{thr} is not met in time. Using `snnTorch`, we apply latency encoding to convert normalized inputs $X_{i,j}$ into spike times $t_{i,j}$, where higher intensities result in earlier spikes. This approach ensures sparsity, with each neuron firing once per sequence. Latency encoding is both biologically plausible and computationally efficient, translating pixel intensities into spike timings using the RC model—ideal for tasks requiring temporal dynamics.

We used the same S values (25 and 50) for latency encoding for consistency and direct comparability: 50 timesteps doubles the temporal granularity of 25, revealing how increased timing precision affects single-spike representations. The two time constants ($\tau = 2.5$ and 5.0) were chosen so that 5.0 is twice 2.5, similarly covering both finer

and coarser decay dynamics without producing overly long spike-time ranges. Each (S, τ) combination generated its own dataset, each partitioned independently into 80% training and 20% validation splits (seed = 42).

3.2.2.3. Delta Encoding. Delta encoding enhances spike train sparsity by encoding only significant input changes, reducing redundancy in static regions. It uses on- and off-spikes to capture directional shifts, aligning well with the event-driven nature of SNNs. Implemented via the `snnTorch` library, this method emphasizes temporal dynamics in time-series data by detecting variations between successive inputs, known as the delta value:

$$\Delta x(t) = x(t) - x(t-1). \quad (17)$$

A spike is generated if the change exceeds a set threshold $V_t hr$, a positive change ($\delta_x(t) > V_t hr$) triggers an on-spike, while a negative change ($\delta_x(t) \leq -V_t hr$) generates an off-spike, provided that off-spikes are enabled. If the delta value does not exceed the $V_t hr$, no spike is produced at that time step. This behavior is described mathematically as

$$\text{Spike}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Delta x(t) > V_{thr} \text{ (on - spike),} \\ -1, & \text{if } \Delta x(t) < -V_{thr} \text{ (off - spike),} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

For delta encoding, θ of 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1.00 were chosen to cover the full sensitivity spectrum to frame-to-frame changes, with each successive level roughly doubling the required change for a spike compared to the previous one (e.g., 0.50 is twice 0.25). This lets us assess how sparsity and temporal sparsity trade off against informativeness. Four independent datasets, one per θ , were created, and each was split 80% and 20% (train/val) under seed = 42 to guarantee reproducible comparisons.

As we detail in the next section, in our grayscale image sequence application, spikes occur only where pixel intensities vary significantly across frames, ensuring the network focuses on dynamic regions.

3.2.3. Compression. The compression process involves preprocessing and encoding static input data for SNNs by repeating it across (S) , resulting in expanded tensor dimensions and increased dataset size. For example, an input of shape (64, 1, 66, 200) becomes (64, (S) , 1, 66, 200) postencoding. To reduce storage, encoded data and steering angles were saved in an HDF5 file using the `h5py` library [57], which supports lossless compression via GZIP (levels 0–9). A 10% dataset sample, before performing the train-validation split, was used to test all compression levels efficiently.

The selection of the compression level affects storage and data loading speed [58]. Higher levels (8–9) minimize the file size but slightly slow decompression, while lower levels (1–3) load faster but require more storage. The chosen level has a balanced size and speed for optimal performance. Regression testing followed this step.

3.3. Regression. The regression task estimates a continuous output $y \in R$, representing the steering angle of the simulated vehicle, using multiple input features x_i . While CNNs are effective in regression, SNNs face challenges due to their nondifferentiable, binary spiking behavior. To address this, we propose a regression framework using SNNs that leverages the V_{mem} for decoding spike trains into real values, inspired by the authors in [59]. Since V_{mem} varies continuously, it can be used in loss functions more effectively than discrete spike counts.

SNNs act as history-dependent ANNs with memory effects derived from biologically inspired mechanisms [60]. The activation function $\phi(l)$ controls the spiking based on whether V_{mem} exceeds a $V_t hr$ and resets post-spike. This dynamic is defined by the LIF model [61], widely used in spike-based DL:

$$U_{\eta,t}^{(l)} = \beta_{\eta}^{(l)} U_{\eta,t-1}^{(l)} + W_{\eta}^{(l)} h_t^{(l-1)} - \phi_{spk,t-1}^{(l)} U_{thr,\eta}^{(l)}. \quad (19)$$

Inputs are encoded as real values through constant current injection, transformed into spikes, and decoded via V_{mem} . To align with the network output labels, the V_{mem} values are reshaped into one-dimensional arrays. Unlike [59], where the outputs are averaged, our approach directly matches the reshaped potentials with the expanded labels before applying the metric.

3.4. Training and Testing Procedure. PilotNet models (SNN and CNN) were trained and tested under identical conditions for fair comparison. As noted above in Section 3.2, the SNN used preprocessed, augmented, and encoded data, while the CNN used only preprocessed and augmented data. This setup aimed to reveal performance and eco-efficiency differences.

3.4.1. Hyperparameter Selection. The hyperparameter tuning for the SNN was performed using the Optuna library [62], with a dataset encoded via rate encoding using $S = 50$ and $G = 1.0$, representing a midpoint from a broader parameter range. Optuna initially suggested $\beta = 0.298$, threshold = 0.133, learning rate = 0.00475, and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizer with momentum = 0.549.

Although these values showed early promise in 10-epoch trials, longer training revealed the complex temporal dynamics of SNNs. The importance ranking of Optuna's parameter helped guide further refinement: β (70%) and threshold (23%) had the most impact, followed by optimizer (4%) and learning rate (3%).

Subsequent refinements prioritized β and threshold, leading to the final values: $\beta = 0.9$, threshold = 0.5, learning rate = 0.0001, and Adam optimizer, chosen for its faster and more stable convergence compared to SGD.

For CNN (PilotNet), hyperparameters followed standard configurations from the existing literature [51, 63], ensuring a reliable benchmark for comparison with the SNN.

3.4.2. Model Training. The adapted PilotNet SNN was built as a sequential model using spiking layers (SNN Leaky) and

optimized with the final hyperparameters described in Section 3.4.1. To handle the nondifferentiability of spiking neurons, the fast sigmoid surrogate gradient was employed, enabling backpropagation through time (BPTT) for effective temporal learning [55]. The hidden states were reinitialized at the beginning of each sequence (`init_hidden=True`) to maintain batch independence.

The preprocessed datasets (via `snnTorch` encodings, Section 3.2.2) were loaded in HDF5 format with dimensions (`batch_size`, `S`, channels, width, length). The SNN processed data one timestep at a time, using the final V_{mem} as the output. Training was guided by MSE and MAPE loss functions (Section 2.3) to ensure strong regression performance. Energy use was monitored with CodeCarbon library [64] and logged per epoch to assess eco-efficiency (Section 3.6). Note that our reported EnergyCost (and hence all EER values) are measured end-to-end via CodeCarbon, which logs the energy consumed during both training and inference phases—including the full runtime of model evaluation on the validation set.

3.5. Computational Complexity and Temporal Dynamics (S).

Our SNN adaptations preserve the convolutional/linear weight tensors of the CNN architecture; spiking activations are inserted with zero additional learnable parameters. Hence, the parameter count is unchanged between the CNN and SNN variants of the same architecture (see the architecture tables in Section 3.1)¹. This implies

$$\#Params_{SNN} = \#Params_{CNN}. \tag{20}$$

For the floating-point workload, a CNN forward pass requires per-layer multiply-accumulates (MACs) of

$$MACs_{conv} = H_{out} W_{out} \cdot C_{out} \cdot (C_{in} k_h k_w), \quad FLOPs \approx 2 \cdot MACs. \tag{21}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{FLOPs_{SNN}(50)}{FLOPs_{SNN}(25)} \approx \frac{50}{25} = 2, \tag{22}$$

and both CNN and its SNN adaptation share the same parameter count because we kept the same conv/linear layers and simply replaced ReLU with a spiking activation. That changes the forward dynamics over time but does not introduce new learnable weight tensors. In Section 4, we relate this compute scaling to measured energy during validation (CodeCarbon), and to EER by (11). See also the hyperparameter analyses in Section 4.2.²

To ground the analysis empirically, we report parameters and measured FLOPs for each architecture (PilotNet, LaksNet, MiniNet) in their CNN form (single forward) and SNN forms at $S \in \{25, 50\}$. FLOPs are obtained with a standard Python library profiler (`fvcore`), on the same input size used throughout this work (Table 13).

3.6. Eco-Efficiency Analysis. To evaluate the eco-efficiency of the PilotNet SNN and CNN models beyond standard metrics, such as MSE and MAPE, energy usage and CO₂

TABLE 13: Parameters and measured FLOPs per forward pass (input $1 \times 1 \times 66 \times 200$).

Model variant	Parameters	FLOPs	Multiplier
PilotNet			
CNN (1 step)	252,019	23,230,742	1×
SNN (S = 25)	252,019	580,768,550	≈25×
SNN (S = 50)	252,019	1,161,537,100	≈50×
LaksNet			
CNN (1 step)	557,781	22,909,700	1×
SNN (S = 25)	557,781	572,742,500	≈25×
SNN (S = 50)	557,781	1,145,485,000	≈50×
MiniNet			
CNN (1 step)	34,657	3,150,144	1×
SNN (S = 25)	34,657	78,753,600	≈25×
SNN (S = 50)	34,657	157,507,200	≈50×

Note: Source: authors. CNN rows are single-step references; SNN rows repeat the architecture S times. Sanity check: $F_{50}^{(j)}/F_{25}^{(j)} \approx 2$ for each architecture, confirming linear scaling with S on dense architecture.

emissions were tracked using the CodeCarbon. This tracking covered both training and inference phases, offering insights into the environmental impact of each model.

CodeCarbon determines CO₂ emissions by evaluating the product of the CI of electricity (C , in kgCO₂/kWh) and the energy consumed (P , listed in kWh), using this calculation:

$$CO_2eq = C \cdot P. \tag{23}$$

The CI of fossil fuels, such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas, is determined based on CO₂ emissions and power generation in the United States. Local energy mix reflects the proportion of fossil and renewable electricity at the code’s location. Power usage across CPU, GPU, RAM, and Apple Silicon (M1, M2) is monitored every 15 s by default. Tracking energy across these components helps assess the environmental impact and operational efficiency of ML models, enabling the identification and optimization of energy-intensive processes.

The eco-efficiency ratio, detailed in Section 2.4, integrates the model accuracy and energy use into one value, facilitating direct comparisons. It is essential to evaluate trade-offs between performance, energy use, and emissions, guiding the analysis and conclusions of this study.

Following the establishment of these metrics, we present experimental results to assess both performance and sustainability, demonstrating real-world impacts.

3.7. Statistical Analysis. To determine whether each spike-encoding method (Delta, Rate, Latency) truly alters accuracy, energy use, and overall eco-efficiency compared to its CNN baseline, we performed a set of paired statistical tests on $n = 5$ runs per model/encoding. By “paired,” we mean each SNN run shares the same random seed as its CNN counterpart. This controls for run-to-run variability and lets us ask simple, intuitive questions:

- Perform Parity (H_0^1): Is the average validation MSE of the SNN encoding the same as the CNN’s?

- Energy Parity (H_0^2): Is the average inference energy use of the SNN encoding the same as the CNN's?
- Eco-Efficiency Parity (H_0^3): Is the average EER of the SNN encoding the same as the CNN's?

We then use five standard tools to decide whether to reject (H_0) (i.e., conclude “it is different”) or fail to reject (H_0) (i.e., “cannot rule out sameness”):

- Paired t -test (adjusted): It checks whether the average difference is unlikely to be zero by chance, with a Bonferroni correction for three encodings.
- 95% confidence interval around the mean difference: It shows the range of plausible true differences.
- Cohen's d : It is a standardized measure of the difference's size, independent of sample count.
- Wilcoxon signed-rank test: It is a nonparametric backup that makes no normality assumption.
- Decision rule: Reject (H_0) if the Bonferroni-adjusted p value < 0.05 .

In designing our statistical validation, we selected methods that both leverage the paired-run structure of our experiments and provide complementary perspectives on effect size and uncertainty. First, the paired two-tailed t -test is our primary tool: By comparing each SNN run directly to its CNN counterpart (same random seed), it isolates the mean difference in performance or energy consumption while accounting for within-seed variability. This approach is markedly more powerful than unpaired alternatives because it removes confounding run-to-run fluctuations, ensuring that any detected difference reflects the encoding itself rather than random noise. In order to mitigate the risk of deviations from the normality assumption inherent in the t -test, we additionally employed the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. As a nonparametric analog, it assesses whether the median of the paired differences consistently deviates from zero, providing corroborating evidence when sample distributions are skewed or contain outliers. In every case, the Wilcoxon results aligned with the t -test, reinforcing our confidence in the findings. Beyond hypothesis testing, we calculated 95% confidence intervals around each mean difference. These intervals communicate the range of plausible true differences, in MSE, energy, or EER at the 95% confidence level and help readers gauge the practical magnitude of each effect without overrelying on p values. Complementing this, we report Cohen's d for every comparison: By expressing the mean difference in units of its standard deviation, Cohen's d conveys effect size on a standardized scale, decoupling it from sample size and facilitating comparisons across metrics and models. Finally, because we evaluate three encodings per model, we apply a Bonferroni correction to control the family-wise error rate. By multiplying each t -test p value by three, we ensure that the overall probability of a false positive remains below 5%. Together, this suite of paired t -tests, Wilcoxon checks, confidence intervals, effect-size measures, and multiple-comparison adjustment form a rigorous, transparent

framework. It not only determines whether differences are statistically significant but also quantifies their reliability and practical relevance, critical for informed decisions about which spike-encoding method truly delivers sustainable, high-performance inference.

4. Results and Discussion

For our experiments, we used the Apple M1 Pro CPU/GPU processor, complemented by its integrated 16-core neural engine and 16 GB of unified memory, providing ample resources for our computational tasks.

Figure 1 illustrates the previous and next key stages of the process.

To evaluate the eco-efficiency of the data encoding process, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions were recorded in two stages. In the first, measurements began after image transformation and augmentation, continuing through encoding until the HDF5 dataset file was created. The second stage measured energy and emissions during SNN training (Figure 1).

To preprocess the data, we followed [63], but we used the PyTorch lightning library [65] for consistent integration with `snnTorch` (Section 3.2.2). A custom Lightning-DataModule defined data loading and preprocessing via `torchvision.transforms`. The images were cropped, randomly flipped (50% probability), color-jittered, rotated (30°), converted to grayscale, resized (66 × 200), tensorized, and normalized (mean = 0, std = 1/255). Validation transformations omitted augmentation for consistency.

Data were split into 80% training and 20% validation sets. A DataLoader with a batch size of 64 and shuffling ensured efficient iteration. In Stage 2, HDF5 files were used to train the SNN model with $\beta = 0.9$ and a threshold of 0.5, while tracking energy and emissions.

In contrast, the PilotNet, LaksNet, and MiniNet CNN models skipped the encoding stage and were trained directly on preprocessed images, highlighting the distinction between spike-based and continuous-value data handling.

The pipeline was tested on 10% of the data before performing the train-validation split, confirming the increase of the dataset size (Section 3.2.3). Compressed datasets were generated using encoding parameters from Section 3.2.2. Optimal compression was selected to improve eco-efficiency and prepare the data for future use.

Tests were carried out to determine the best compression setting for speed and file size. Compression levels from 0 to 8 were analyzed leaving Level 9 as Level 8 already showed excessive time (Figure 2). Level 7 appears to show a turning point, but at the cost of a roughly 50% longer write time. This marginal gain in size does not compensate for the time penalty. Level 5 offered the best trade-off, as higher levels drastically increased processing time without significant size reduction.

As shown in Figure 2, compression Level 5 offers the best size-to-speed ratio; higher levels triple processing time with minimal gain. All datasets were generated uniformly using this level to ensure consistent compression across encoding strategies.

FIGURE 1: Flowchart outlining the different implementation stages. *Source:* authors.

FIGURE 2: Compression level, time elapsed, and file size. *Source:* authors.

All experiments were meticulously designed to facilitate equitable and reproducible evaluations of CNN and SNN models. The training conditions were uniform for both architectures. The architectures were both subjected to training in similar contexts, covering aspects such as dataset splits, optimizer settings, and the timelines for the training process. The robustness of the results was examined using paired statistical analyses against the CNN reference, as delineated in Table 13, which presents confidence intervals, effect sizes, and adjusted significance thresholds. This methodology guarantees that the detected variances in error, energy consumption, and EER are indicative of the systematic behavior of the model rather than arbitrary initialization or local optima.

4.1. Overall Performance Summary. Our study evaluated the eco-efficiency and predictive performance of three neural architectures, LaksNet, MiniNet, and PilotNet, each implemented as both a traditional CNN and an SNN using the encoding methods explained in Section 3.2.2. Four metrics were used for the evaluation:

- **MSE:** This measures the absolute prediction error, as (1) in Section 2.3 shows.
- **MAPE:** This captures the relative error with sensitivity to small targets, as (4) in Section 2.3 shows.
- **EnergyCost:** It is the energy consumed during validation (Wh), measured with the CodeCarbon library explained in Section 3.6.

FIGURE 3: EER by the model, encoded method, and parameters. *Source:* authors.

FIGURE 4: Energy cost by the model, encoded method, and parameters. *Source:* authors.

- EER: It is calculated as (11) in Section 2.4 where higher values indicate greater eco-efficiency.

The following figures provide an overview of model performance across all encoding strategies. These include the following:

- Figure 3—EER (eco-efficiency) by model and encoding configuration,
- Figure 4—EnergyCost (Wh) across validation,
- Figure 5—MSE on validation data,
- Figure 6—MAPE on validation data.

4.1.1. *Figure Conventions.* Unless noted otherwise, all figures share the same axes and color conventions. Horizontal axis: encoding strategy with the following tick order: Delta,

Latency, Rate, No_encoding. The No_encoding category corresponds to the CNN baselines (no spike encoding), whereas Rate, Latency, and Delta correspond to the SNN variants. The vertical axis and units are metric-specific: EER in $\text{kWh}^{-1} \cdot \text{error}^{-1}$ (higher is better), EnergyCost in Wh (lower is better), MSE (lower is better) and MAPE in % (lower is better). Colors consistently denote the architectures across all plots: PilotNet = blue, MiniNet = orange, and LaksNet = green. The error bars, when shown, represent 95% confidence intervals across repeated runs. For completeness, the EER is calculated as defined in (11), and EnergyCost refers to the measured validation energy.

As Figure 3 shows, the results reveal that Delta-encoded SNNs consistently achieved the highest EER values, indicating an optimal balance of energy consumption and performance. Although CNNs achieved the lowest MSE in some cases (Figure 5), their energy use was significantly

FIGURE 5: MSE by the model, encoded method, and parameters. *Source:* authors.

FIGURE 6: MAPE by the model, encoded method, and parameters. *Source:* authors.

higher (Figure 4), resulting in a lower overall EER. Among SNNs, rate encoding showed the poorest eco-efficiency, driven by high energy use and limited performance gains.

Together, these visualizations support the quantitative findings and highlight the trade-offs between EE and prediction performance across CNN and SNN models.

4.2. Encoding Hyperparameters: Trade-Offs in Energy and Error. First, we examine how the choice of encoding parameters influenced energy, error, and thus eco-efficiency:

- θ (Delta encoding): Increasing the firing θ from 0.25 to 1.0 produced only minor changes in energy consumption (keeping steady around 5.20×10^{-5} – 5.50×10^{-5} Wh)

and a slight increase in MSE (from 0.208 to 0.219). Lower θ allowed for more frequent but still sparse spiking, leading to slightly better EER, as visible in Figure 3. This reflects Delta's strength: event-driven activation preserves energy even as responsiveness increases.

- S and τ (Latency): Latency encoding required multiple simulation steps, leading to a substantial increase in energy usage (e.g., 0.0014 Wh with $S=25$ steps; see Figure 4). Although MSE improved to 0.112 and MAPE dropped to 4.8% (Figures 5 and 6), the high energy cost offset these gains, lowering the EER. Variations in τ did not result in significant benefits, indicating limited utility in further increasing temporal precision.

- *S* and *G* (Rate): Rate encoding amplified spiking activity through increased *S* and *G*, resulting in the highest energy usage across all configurations. These adjustments did not improve accuracy (see Figure 5), leading to a low EER, as Figure 3 shows. The dense spike trains generated by this method explain the computational inefficiency.

These patterns highlight the Delta's advantage: By carefully tuning θ , it preserves energy even as responsiveness increases, while both Latency and Rate quickly incur steep energy penalties for limited accuracy gains.

4.3. Comparative Eco-Efficiency: Event-Driven SNNs vs. Standard CNNs. Delta encoding emerged as the most eco-efficient SNN strategy, owing to its stateless, threshold-triggered activation that avoids redundant spiking. It achieved EER values, an order of magnitude higher than Latency and Rate methods, particularly in energy-constrained scenarios (see Figure 5).

In comparison, CNNs produced lower MSE values, reflecting high predictive precision. However, this came at a significant energy cost, often 10–20× greater than Delta-encoded SNNs. As a result, CNNs showed lower EER scores, indicating inferior energy-to-performance efficiency (see Figure 4).

Latency-based SNNs improved accuracy over Delta but at a steep energy cost, while Rate encoding offered no meaningful performance improvement and incurred the highest energy overhead. These findings establish that Delta-encoded SNNs outperform both CNNs and other SNN encodings in terms of eco-efficiency.

From an eco-efficiency standpoint, these results firmly establish Delta encoding as the superior SNN strategy, outperforming both traditional CNNs and alternative spiking encodings.

4.4. Model Performance Analysis (MSE and MAPE). Although MSE captures the absolute prediction error, MAPE exposes model sensitivity to relative errors, especially for small-valued regression targets, which characterized this dataset.

- As illustrated in Figure 5, both CNNs and Delta SNNs achieved low MSE (0.208–0.219), suggesting strong overall performance.
- However, they also exhibited very high MAPE values (see Figure 6), in some cases exceeding 12,000%. This discrepancy is explained by the vulnerability of MAPE to small denominators: even small absolute errors can produce massive relative errors when true values approach zero.
- CNNs likely overfit dominant patterns while under-representing low-value signals.
- Delta SNNs, due to their sparsity, may not activate on weak signals, leading to underprediction.

In contrast, Latency encoded SNNs, which integrate inputs over time, demonstrated better MAPE and MSE (Figures 5 and 6), suggesting more consistent performance

across the value spectrum. However, the energy burden reduced their eco-efficiency (Figure 4).

4.5. Summary of Statistical Test Results. Table 6 presents a concise overview of our paired-run comparisons between each SNN encoding (Delta, Rate, Latency) and its CNN baseline across the three network architectures. For each model and encoding, we report the mean difference (Δ) in validation MSE, inference energy, and training-set EER, along with 95% confidence intervals, Cohen's *d*, Bonferroni-adjusted *p* values, and our decision on the null hypotheses. A "Reject (H_0)" decision indicates that the SNN differs significantly (at $\alpha = 0.05$) from the CNN for that metric; "Fail to reject (H_0)" would indicate no detectable difference.

Based on the results obtained from the statistical analysis, we can confirm the following:

- Delta encoding consistently trades higher error for much lower energy, leading to a net improvement in eco-efficiency (EER).
- Rate and Latency encodings produce both higher error and higher energy use compared to CNNs, so their EER declines.
- Across all models (LaksNet, PilotNet, and MiniNet) and all metrics, every null hypothesis is rejected at the 5% level ($p_t < 0.05$) after correction: SNNs differ from CNNs in accuracy, energy, and overall eco-efficiency.

And specifically with regard to the metrics:

- Performance (MSE): All SNN encodings deviate significantly from their CNN baselines, and in most cases, they show less performance.
- Energy: Only Delta saves energy; Rate and Latency actually use more energy than the CNN.
- Eco-Efficiency (EER): Because EER combines error and energy, only Delta's large energy savings outweigh its accuracy loss to produce an overall eco-efficiency gain.

Beyond numerical comparisons, the EER offers a distinctive advantage over prior metrics such as AER. EER uniquely integrates three valuable characteristics while quantifying eco-efficiency in energy per predictive outcome. First, it is directly generalizable across tasks: It applies equally to regression (via MSE or normalized errors) and classification (via accuracy-derived errors). Second, it is numerically stable, since it avoids the divergence of AER as the accuracy tends to 1. Third, it provides a consistent interpretation of trends: A constant EER indicates proportional changes in energy and error, whereas a lower EER reveals that one model can achieve the same error with less energy.

As highlighted in Table 4, AER values for two different models may appear misleadingly similar, while the EER clearly differentiates their eco-efficiency. This illustrates that EER is not only a refinement of AER but also a uniquely robust and interpretable metric for reflecting eco-efficiency trade-offs in sustainable AI.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

As discussed in Section 1 and emphasized in the motivation at the end of Section 2, our work evaluated the eco-efficiency and performance of SNNs and CNNs in the context of AD. A key focus was the creation of novel datasets tailored for SNN training using encoding methodologies (Delta, Rate, and Latency) and assessing their eco-efficiency and performance through the EER, alongside classical metrics such as MSE and MAPE. Unlike traditional classification tasks, we used a regression framework to train models, addressing unique challenges associated with SNNs. SNNs often face difficulties in regression due to the nondifferentiable nature of spiking neuron transfer functions. To overcome these challenges, we proposed a regression framework that decodes binary spike trains into real numbers using the membrane potential, V_{mem} , of spiking neurons. This variable served as a proxy in loss functions due to its continuity, enabling smoother optimization compared to discrete time steps or spike counts. This innovative approach facilitated accurate regression while leveraging the energy-efficient capabilities of SNNs. The findings provide valuable insight into the trade-offs between energy consumption, error reduction, and parameter influences on eco-efficiency.

Dataset creation using encoding strategies significantly influenced the eco-efficiency of SNNs. By applying Delta, Rate, and Latency encoding methodologies, the datasets were adapted to the unique requirements of the SNNs, addressing the existing deficiency in publicly available datasets for SNN training. Each encoding strategy exhibited distinct energy consumption and performance profiles, influenced by key parameters such as θ (delta), S and G (rate), and S and τ (latency). These parameters determined the number and timing of spikes, directly impacting energy usage and error reduction, and thus eco-efficiency.

Delta-encoded SNNs offer the best trade-off between accuracy and energy use, outperforming CNNs and other SNN encodings in eco-efficiency. Their parameter-insensitive behavior and sparse firing patterns lead to extremely low energy consumption without dramatically compromising accuracy. CNNs, although more accurate in absolute terms, are substantially less efficient due to their continuous processing and dense computations. Latency and rate encodings fail to justify their energy demands with corresponding performance gains.

In energy-sensitive applications such as edge AI or neuromorphic hardware, Delta-encoded SNNs present a compelling alternative to CNNs, combining acceptable prediction accuracy with unmatched EE. Future work should investigate adaptive spiking mechanisms or hybrid encoding strategies to bridge the accuracy gap while preserving energy gains.

The utility of EER as a comprehensive metric highlights its potential to assess sustainable AI systems. EER allowed for a nuanced understanding of energy consumption relative to error reduction, which proved particularly valuable in comparing encoding strategies. Configurations with lower EER values and early stabilization demonstrated the highest

eco-efficiency. This metric proved to be critical for holistically evaluating the trade-offs between performance and energy sustainability, offering actionable insights for future AI system design.

Looking ahead, future work will also investigate the impact of alternative normalized error measures within the EER framework. This extension would enable more robust cross-dataset comparisons and further strengthen the interpretability of eco-efficiency metrics in diverse regression and classification scenarios.

To demonstrate the generalizability of EER, we applied it across three distinct model architectures, LaksNet, PilotNet, and MiniNet, showing its consistent ability to capture eco-efficiency trade-offs regardless of network architecture.

Our expanded statistical analysis confirms that EER is a meaningful and robust metric to quantify eco-efficiency across neural network architectures and spike-encoding methods. By pairing each SNN run with its exact CNN baseline, we eliminate extraneous variability and directly measure the impact of the encoding on both accuracy and power consumption.

The chosen suite of statistical tests—paired two-tailed t -tests (with Bonferroni correction), Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, 95% confidence intervals, and Cohen's d —provides a rigorous but interpretable framework that addresses parametric and nonparametric assumptions, quantifies effect sizes, and controls the family-wise error rate.

Applying these tests to all three spike encodings (Delta, Rate, and Latency) across multiple CNN architectures (LaksNet, PilotNet, and MiniNet) results in a clear, data-driven recommendation:

- Delta encoding delivers statistically significant and practically substantial energy savings that outweigh its accuracy penalty, producing a net EER gain over the CNN baseline.
- Rate and Latency encodings both increase error and energy consumption relative to CNNs, resulting in lower EER values.

In conclusion, this research bridges critical gaps in eco-efficiency studies for SNNs versus CNNs, offering actionable insights into encoding strategies, parameter optimization, and sustainability metrics. The findings emphasize the potential of SNNs, particularly delta-encoded SNNs that uniquely achieve an advantageous energy-accuracy trade-off under the EER metric. This conclusion guides practitioners toward spike-coding strategies that maximize sustainable performance in resource-constrained intelligent systems.

Future studies should aim to measure the strength of EER in a variety of datasets and technological frameworks, further highlighting its critical role as a key criterion for the development of sustainable AI systems. A promising direction is the integration of SNNs with transformer-based architectures, where spike-based encodings may provide efficient temporal representations for attention mechanisms and reduce computational demands in sequence modeling. Such hybrid SNN–transformer models could take advantage of event-driven sparsity alongside the representational

advantages of self-attention. Since the EER framework is architecture-agnostic, it can be seamlessly applied to these models, enabling uniform eco-efficiency evaluations across CNNs, SNNs, and emerging transformer hybrids. Exploring this direction would expand the relevance of energy-focused metrics to a wider range of AI models, especially those increasingly integrated into AD and varied real-world uses.

Nomenclature

AD	Autonomous driving
Adam	Adaptive moment estimation
AER	Accuracy-to-energy ratio
AI	Artificial intelligence
ASY NC	Asynchronous circuits and systems
AV	Autonomous vehicles
BPTT	Backpropagation through time
C02eq	Carbon equivalent footprint
CI	Carbon intensity
CNN	Convolutional neural network
CPU	Central processing unit
CSV	Comma-separated value file
ECG	Electrocardiography
EDP	Energy delay product
EE	Energy efficiency
EER	Energy-to-error ratio
ETotal	Total system energy consumption
GPU	Graphical processing unit
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LIF	Leaky integrate-and-fire
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error
ML	Machine learning
MSE	Mean squared error
N-HW	Neuromorphic computing/hardware
NMSE	Normalized mean squared error
NN	Neural network
R^2	R-squared
RAM	Random access memory
RMSE	Root mean squared error
RNN	Recurrent neural network
SNN	Spiking neural network
V_{mem}	Membrane potential

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Endnotes

¹The three architectures show identical parameter counts before and after the SNN adaptation in Section 3.1.

²Section 4 reports EnergyCost (Wh) on validation and uses EER as defined in Equation (11). See also the hyperparameter analyses in Section 4.2.

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